

Multi-Stakeholder Engagement in Community-Based Tourism Development: Evidence from Pante Makassar, Timor-Leste

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Abstract: This study examined the stakeholders' engagement in Community-Based Tourism (CBT) in Pante Makasar, Oe-Cusse, Timor-Leste. The stakeholders included the local community, the private sector, tourists, and the government. A stakeholder survey was conducted, yielding 331 respondents. The data were analyzed using correlation and regression analysis. The results showed statistically significant positive correlation relationships between community-based tourism and all predictor variables. Additionally, there are significant associations among the local community, the private sector, and tourists regarding community-based tourism; however, no statistically significant relationships have been found between the local government and community-based tourism development in Pante Makasar. The results of this study revealed the essential role of stakeholders in community-based tourism development, which enhances the local community economy.

Keywords: Local Communities, Private Sector, Local Government, Tourists, Community-Based Tourism

1. Introduction

Tourism is a key driver of economic growth, social development, and cultural preservation, particularly in regions with rich natural and cultural heritage (UNWTO, 2022; Lemunge et al., 2025). Community-based tourism (CBT) is a sustainable approach involving local communities in planning, managing, and benefiting from tourism activities (Goodwin & Santilli, 2009; Wani et al.,

2024). Unlike mass tourism, CBT emphasizes local ownership, equitable benefit-sharing, and the conservation of cultural and natural resources. Multi-stakeholder engagement is crucial for the success of CBT, as it requires collaboration among community members, local government, the private sector, and tourists to ensure long-term sustainability (Jamal & Stronza, 2009; Lee & Joo, 2024). In Pante Makassar, a region with significant potential for community-based tourism, understanding the roles of different stakeholders in tourism development is essential to creating a sustainable, inclusive tourism model.

Despite increasing recognition of community-based tourism as a sustainable development strategy, stakeholder collaboration continues to pose persistent challenges, particularly in developing regions (Bramwell & Lane, 2011; Wani et al., 2024). A lack of capacity often hinders local community involvement, limits access to financial resources, and results in inadequate policy support (Tosun, 2000). Similarly, the role of the private sector remains ambiguous, as businesses may prioritize profit over sustainability, leading to conflicts with local interests (Hall, 2011). Moreover, local governments in developing countries often face governance and coordination challenges, limiting their effectiveness in implementing sustainable tourism policies (Nunkoo, 2015). Tourists also play a vital role in shaping tourism experiences, but their level of engagement in CBT initiatives is often overlooked in research and policy discussions (Lemunge et al., 2025; Scheyvens, 2002).

While previous studies have explored stakeholder involvement in tourism development, there remains a gap in understanding how these different actors interact and contribute to CBT in Pante Makassar, a unique region in Timor-Leste. Existing CBT literature primarily focuses on community participation (Lee & Joo, 2024; Okazaki, 2008) or government interventions (Sofield, 2003), with limited research examining the interconnected roles of multiple stakeholders in a single framework. Additionally, studies on tourism in Timor-Leste remain scarce, leaving a knowledge gap regarding the specific challenges and opportunities in this context. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing an integrated approach that enhances stakeholder collaboration and promotes sustainable community tourism in Pante Makassar.

In addition, although previous studies on community-based tourism have extensively examined community participation, private-sector involvement, and government roles in isolation, they have largely failed to analyze these stakeholders simultaneously within a single empirical framework, particularly in small, post-conflict island contexts such as Timor-Leste. Existing research often emphasizes qualitative case studies or focuses on policy analysis without quantitatively testing the relative and combined effects of multiple stakeholder groups on CBT outcomes. Moreover,

empirical evidence from RAE OA and Pante Makassar remains extremely limited, leaving a contextual gap in understanding how local socio-institutional conditions shape stakeholder engagement. This study addresses these gaps by employing a quantitative survey to simultaneously examine the roles of the community, private sector, local government, and tourists, thereby providing comparative, statistically grounded evidence on their individual and collective contributions to CBT development in Pante Makassar, RAE OA.

This study investigates multi-stakeholder engagement in community-based tourism development in Pante Makassar by analyzing the roles of the community, the private sector, the local government, and tourists. It seeks to identify the key factors influencing stakeholder participation and the challenges hindering effective collaboration. By adopting a holistic perspective, this research will contribute to the growing body of literature on CBT by offering insights into the dynamics of stakeholder involvement in a developing tourism destination. Furthermore, the findings will provide policy recommendations for fostering inclusive and sustainable tourism development in Pante Makassar. Furthermore, understanding stakeholder interactions is vital to the success of community-based tourism in Pante Makassar, Timor-Leste. While CBT offers significant potential for economic, social, and cultural development, its effectiveness depends on the active participation and cooperation of all key stakeholders. By addressing existing research gaps and comprehensively analyzing stakeholder engagement, this study will provide valuable insights to improve tourism governance and ensure long-term benefits for the local community. The remaining research will include the literature review, methodology, results, discussion, conclusions, recommendations, limitations, and future recommendations.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Despite the growing potential of community-based tourism in Pante Makassar, its development has been constrained by weak coordination among key stakeholders, including the local community, private sector, local government, and tourists. Stakeholder roles often operate in isolation, with limited communication, collaboration, and shared planning mechanisms, resulting in fragmented tourism initiatives and underutilization of local resources. The absence of an integrated coordination framework has led to overlapping responsibilities, inconsistent policy implementation, and limited alignment between community needs and private or institutional interventions. These coordination gaps reduce the effectiveness of tourism development efforts and hinder the sustainability of community-based tourism in Pante Makassar. Therefore, understanding how stakeholder coordination functions and identifying areas of weakness is essential for

improving collaborative governance and enhancing the overall effectiveness of community-based tourism development in the region.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the extent to which multi-stakeholder engagement influences the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar, Oe-Cusse. The specific purpose is to:

- (a) To examine the influence of community involvement on the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar.
- (b) To assess the impact of the private sector participation on the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar.
- (c) To examine the local government's influence on the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar.
- (d) To assess the engagement of tourists for the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) How does community involvement influence the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar?
- (b) How does the private sector's participation influence the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar?
- (c) How does the local government support influence the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar?
- (d) How does the engagement of tourists influence the development of community-based tourism in Pante Makasar?

1.4. Hypotheses

The following research hypothesis of the study:

- (a) H1: Community involvement has a significant positive effect on community-based tourism development.
- (b) H2: Private-sector participation positively influences community-based tourism development.

- (c) H3: Local government support is crucial in facilitating community-based tourism development.
- (d) H4: Tourists' engagement significantly impacts the growth of community-based tourism.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design of the study

This study employs a quantitative research approach to explore the roles of the community, private sector, local government, and tourists in the development of community-based tourism (CBT) in Pante Makassar. A survey-based quantitative design was chosen because it allows systematic measurement and statistical comparison of perceptions and levels of involvement across multiple stakeholder groups, making it suitable for testing relationships between stakeholder engagement and community-based tourism development. The research employs a survey-based method to collect primary data from the identified stakeholders through structured questionnaires, with a scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (Brites da Silva et al., 2021; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

2.1.1 Ethics Statement

This study strictly adhered to established ethical standards for research involving human participants, obtaining ethical approval from the relevant institutional and department-level graduate school review boards before any data collection to ensure compliance with the principles of voluntary participation, confidentiality, and respect for participants' rights. All respondents were given a clear, comprehensive informed consent form that explained the research's purpose and their involvement, including their right to withdraw without penalty, and written consent was secured from every participant before commencing the survey. Furthermore, to protect participant privacy and dignity throughout the research process, they were assured that their responses would be anonymized and used exclusively for academic purposes, with no personal identifiers included in the analysis or publication of the findings.

2.2 Area of Study

This research was primarily conducted in Pante Makasar, the capital of the Oe-cusse municipality in Timor-Leste. This area is a special region or enclave on Timor Island that was surrounded by Indonesian territory.

2.3 *Population and Sample*

A sample size was determined using the Slovin formula with a 6% margin of error to estimate the appropriate sample size for this study (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Substituting these values into the formula results in a calculated sample size of 331 participants. This sample size provides 94% confidence and a 6% margin of error, which is considered statistically sufficient for obtaining reliable, representative results. The formula was applied using the assumption of maximum variability to ensure the robustness of the findings, given that no prior population data were available (Cochran, 1977).

2.4 *Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure*

This research was conducted using a survey or by delivering questionnaires to participants. The questionnaires were developed based on a literature review and previous theories and studies by Abreu et al. (2024), Goodwin & Santilli (2009), Wani et al. (2024), Bramwell & Lane (2011), Sharma et al. (2022), and Tosun et al (2025). There are five statements for each of the four significant variables in community-based tourism: community involvement, local government involvement, local tourists' involvement, and private sector involvement. Firstly, the indicators for community involvement include (Community knowledge contributes significantly to the development of community-based tourism; Local communities can generate income from the products they sell at tourism sites; Local communities also gain access to improved facilities within these areas; The characteristics and cultural identity of the local community become strengthened and present high value and appeal for tourists; In addition, safety and security must be ensured in community-based tourism destinations). Secondly, the indicators for the private sector include: (The private sector and related industries must be actively involved in the development of community-based tourism; The private sector is responsible for providing the facilities and basic services tourists need at tourism sites; The income of private-sector actors and industries will increase through business activities; Services offered to tourists must be delivered with quality and professionalism; Furthermore, the private sector requires financial support and training to strengthen its capacity and contribute effectively to community-based tourism development). Thirdly, the indicators for tourists' involvement include (Tourists require unique attractions at tourism sites; They need access to adequate infrastructure and quality facilities in community-based tourism destinations; Tourists also expect a friendly environment and a strong, welcoming local culture; In addition, tourists require guaranteed security, available 24 hours a day and seven days a week, both within the community and at tourism locations; Tourists must also have easy access

to basic daily necessities in various places while spending their leisure time at community-based tourism sites). Lastly, the indicators for local government involvement include (The local government is responsible for establishing laws and regulations to guide and govern tourism development; It also formulates policy programs that support the advancement of community-based tourism; The local government prepares annual activity plans for community-based tourism development and provides financial support to other stakeholders involved in this sector; In addition, the local government offers education, training, and necessary facilities to stakeholders to strengthen the development of community-based tourism directly).

2.5 Data Collection Technique

To gather the necessary data for this quantitative research, the researcher administered a questionnaire, as noted by Brites da Silva et al. (2021). The primary goal was to test hypotheses and collect initial data from participants. Crucially, the researcher first conducted a pre-test of the questionnaire with 30 respondents. This step was essential to verify the clarity and understanding of the items. The feedback received during this pre-test was then used to refine the instrument, thereby helping to minimize potential bias in the final research data.

2.5 Data Analysis Technique

This study analyzed data using SPSS 29, employing both ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) and multiple regression analysis to examine the relationships between stakeholder engagement and community-based tourism development. ANOVA was used to assess whether there are statistically significant differences in tourism development outcomes across stakeholder groups, including the community, private sector, local government, and tourists. This technique would help identify whether the mean scores of other groups differ significantly. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the predictive power of various stakeholder roles, including community involvement, private sector participation, government support, and tourist engagement, on tourism development outcomes. The regression model would allow for testing the combined effect of multiple independent variables on a dependent variable, providing insights into how each stakeholder's involvement influences community-based tourism development. Using SPSS 29, these statistical techniques would help to conclude the impact of multi-stakeholder engagement on tourism development and sustainability (Pallant, 2020; Field, 2013).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Demographic information of the respondents: description and discussion

The study involved a total of 331 respondents representing the four key stakeholder groups in community-based tourism (CBT) in Pante Makassar: local community members, private sector actors, government officials, and tourists. Among these, 73% were local community members, 10% were from the private sector, 11% were government officials, and 6% were tourists. In terms of gender distribution, 63% of respondents were male, and 37% were female, reflecting a balanced perspective from both genders. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 60 years, with the majority (60%) aged 25 to 45, indicating that most respondents were of working age and likely actively involved in tourism-related activities. Educational backgrounds varied among stakeholders: community members primarily had secondary education. In contrast, private-sector and government participants had higher levels of education, which may influence their understanding and involvement in tourism planning and management. This demographic information means each stakeholder group contributes differently to CBT development. For example, local communities provide labor, cultural knowledge, and social capital, directly impacting tourism activities. At the same time, the private sector offers investment, infrastructure, and market knowledge that shape the economic viability of tourism. Government officials influence regulatory frameworks, policy implementation, and public support, whereas tourists drive demand and shape service offerings through their preferences and behavior. The distribution of respondents ensures that the perspectives of all major actors are captured, allowing for a more nuanced analysis of multi-stakeholder engagement. Differences in age, education, and role also help explain variations in responses, highlighting which stakeholder groups have stronger or weaker perceptions of their involvement and the impact of tourism development.

Table 1: Reliability test of variables.

Variables	CA	CR	AVE
CBT	0.786	0.843	0.524
Community Involvement	0.601	0.768	0.529

Private Sector Involvement	0.704	0.814	0.524
Tourist Involvement	0.709	0.817	0.530
Local Government Involvement	0.766	0.847	0.585

Note: CA = Cronbach Alpha, CR= Composite Reliability, and AVE= Average Variance Extracted

3.2 Description

Table 1 above illustrates the reliability alphas for various constructs. The coefficient alpha (CA) and composite reliability (CR) for all variables exceed 0.7, which is an acceptable threshold according to the research standards (Hair et al., 2018). Furthermore, the Cronbach's Alpha (CA) assesses internal consistency under the assumption of equal indicator loadings. At the same time, the Composite Reliability (CR) provides a more robust reliability estimate that accounts for differing indicator loadings, thereby strengthening the measurement reliability assessment (Hair et al., 2018).

Table 2: Correlation between CBT and Associated Variables.

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
CBT	1				
Community Involvement	0.454**	1			
Private Sector involvement	0.433**	0.462**	1		
Tourist Involvement	0.542**	0.479**	0.347**	1	
Local Government Involvement	0.412**	0.400**	0.347**	0.330**	1

Notes: ** = p-value less than 0.00

3.3 Description

The results of the correlation analysis indicated that relationships between Community-Based tourism development and the predictor variables were significant for all four predictor variables (See Table 2). The most positive association, Pearson correlation, was between CBT and tourists ($r = 0.542$), followed by a positive association between community involvement and CBT ($r = 0.454$). This was followed by a correlation between the private sector and CDT ($r = 0.433$), and, lastly, the local government also showed a significant correlation with CBT ($r = 0.412$).

Table 3: Result of Multiple Regression Analysis.

Model	Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	<i>t & P-value</i>
1	(Constant)	1.160		5.048**
	Community Involvement	0.152	0.152	2.747**
	Private Sector Involvement	0.198	0.205	3.876**
	Tourist Involvement	0.351	0.343	6.208**
	Local Government Involvement	0.058	0.067	0.183

*Notes: Dependent Variables = CBT. N = 331. **p<0.001*

Table 4. R-Square result

Adjusted R2	R2 change
0.365	0.373

3.4 Description

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of four predicted variables on the dependent variable, Community-Based tourism development (See Table 3). The result indicated that local community involvement was positively related to CBT ($\beta = 0.152$; $p < 0.00$). This means a unit increase in local community participation, which will be a 0.152 increase in CBT. In addition, private-sector involvement is positively associated with CBT ($\beta = 0.205$; $p < 0.00$). This means a unit increase in private-sector involvement, which will be a 0.205 increase in CBT. Also, the tourist's involvement is significantly associated with CBT ($\beta = 0.343$; $p < 0.00$). This means a unit increase in tourists' participation, resulting in a 0.343 increase in CBT. However, local government involvement is not statistically significantly related to CBT ($\beta = 0.067$; $p\text{-value} = 0.183$). This could mean that local government is less involved in CBT development in the local area of this study. Furthermore, in terms of the R-square result (See Table 4), this indicates that the independent variables of community participation, the private sector, local government, and tourists explain 37.3 percent of CBT. Thus, other remaining variables might influence the development of CBT in this study area.

3.5 Discussion

This study examined the predicted variables of local community, private sector, tourist, and local government involvement in community-based tourism development in Pante Makasar, Oe-Cusse, and Timor-Leste. The following explains the statistical relationships of each hypothesis.

H1. The findings of this study indicate that local community involvement is positively related to the success of community-based tourism (CBT) development, aligning with previous research that emphasizes the crucial role of community participation in fostering sustainable tourism practices. According to Tosun (2000) and Lemunge et al. (2025), community involvement ensures that tourism development meets local needs, promotes cultural preservation, and generates economic benefits for residents. Furthermore, studies by Scheyvens (2002), Goodwin (2011), Ruiz-Ballesteros & González-Portillo, (2024), and Gutierrez (2022) argue that when communities actively participate in decision-making processes, they are more likely to support tourism initiatives, ensuring the industry's long-term sustainability. Thus, the positive relationship between local community involvement and CBT in this study corroborates prior findings and underscores the importance of community participation for successful tourism outcomes.

H2. The findings of this study also reveal that private-sector involvement is positively associated with the success of community-based tourism (CBT) development, consistent with prior research highlighting the essential role of businesses in fostering tourism growth. Dredge and

Jenkins (2007), Abreu et al (2024), Hall (2008), and Bramwell and Lane (2011) state that the private sector provides the financial resources, infrastructure, and marketing expertise necessary for tourism development, particularly in community-based initiatives. The private sector's investment in local businesses, including accommodations, tours, and attractions, directly enhances the local economy, while partnerships with the community ensure that tourism benefits are equitably shared. This study's results support these findings, demonstrating that private-sector engagement not only boosts the economic viability of CBT but also promotes tourism that respects local culture and the environment.

H3. The results of this study also indicate that tourist involvement is significantly associated with the success of community-based tourism (CBT), further supporting previous research that highlights the importance of tourists in promoting sustainable tourism practices. According to Reimer and Walter (2013) and Wani et al (2024), tourists are not merely consumers of tourism experiences but also active participants whose behaviors and preferences can shape the development and sustainability of tourism destinations. When tourists engage with local communities and their culture, they not only help preserve traditions but also generate income for local businesses (Sharpley, 2014). These results underscore the crucial role tourists play in sustaining CBT initiatives, demonstrating that their active engagement yields more positive outcomes for both communities and the tourism industry.

H4. Interestingly, the study finds that local government involvement is statistically not significantly related to the success of community-based tourism (CBT) in Pante Makassar, RAEOA, which contrasts with prior research that emphasizes the critical role of government in tourism development. While government support is often cited as essential for providing infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and policy guidance (Tosun, 2006; Hall, 2008; Lee & Joo, 2024; Sharma et al., 2022), this study's findings suggest that local government engagement may not be as impactful as expected in this specific context. Previous studies, such as those by Byrd (2007) and Okazaki (2008), argue that local governments play a pivotal role in facilitating CBT by ensuring that tourism development is aligned with community needs and sustainable practices. While this study found that local government involvement was not significantly related to community-based tourism (CBT) development in Pantemakassar, RAEOA, it is important to contextualize this finding within the specific governance challenges of Timor-Leste. Local governments across the country often face resource constraints, limited administrative capacity, and human capital shortages, which can constrain their ability to implement effective tourism policies and support community initiatives (World Bank, 2020). Additionally, bureaucratic

inefficiencies, fragmented coordination between municipal and national authorities, and unclear regulatory frameworks can hinder timely decision-making and reduce government responsiveness to community needs (Booth, 2016). Political instability and limited experience in decentralized governance further exacerbate these challenges, leading to inconsistent support for community-based tourism projects. These systemic constraints may explain why the study found a limited impact of government involvement on CBT outcomes, despite its theoretically important role, highlighting the need for capacity-building, improved policy coordination, and stronger institutional support to enable local governments to contribute effectively to sustainable tourism development in Timor-Leste.

Implication:

These study findings have significant implications for the development of community-based tourism in the Pante Makassar. The role of the community, private sector, local government, and tourists is crucial in developing CBT tourism, which benefits the community and can also increase local income. However, the local government has no association with the CBT in Pante Makassar yet; this might be due to limited budgetary resources and some policies not being implemented effectively.

Limitation:

While offering valuable insights into the roles of various stakeholders in community-based tourism (CBT) development in Pante Makassar, this study acknowledges several limitations; it is essential to clarify how these may have influenced the results. First, the dominance of local community respondents over tourists and government officers may have introduced sample bias, potentially amplifying community perspectives while underrepresenting institutional and visitor viewpoints, thereby affecting the relative strength of relationships observed among stakeholder variables. Second, self-reported questionnaire data may be subject to social desirability and recall bias, as respondents may overestimate their level of involvement or the positive impacts of tourism. These factors may have influenced the significance of the statistical relationships identified, particularly for stakeholders with smaller sample representation.

Suggestions for further studies:

Future studies could explore the reasons behind the lack of a significant effect of local government involvement. It might involve investigating barriers to local government support, such

as limited resources, governance inefficiencies, or inadequate policy implementation. Therefore, it could add more significance to the study of CBT.

4. Conclusion

This study examined multi-stakeholder engagement in community-based tourism development in Pante Makassar, RAEOA, and found that community involvement, private-sector participation, and tourist engagement are significantly and positively associated with the success of CBT, highlighting the central role of active stakeholder participation in sustaining local tourism initiatives. In contrast, local government involvement was not found to be statistically significantly associated with CBT, suggesting challenges in policy implementation, resource constraints, and coordination at the regional level. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of strengthening collaborative mechanisms among non-government stakeholders while addressing governance gaps to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of community-based tourism in Pante Makassar.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest in this study.

Author Contributions

The first author serves as the supervisor throughout the research process, including data analysis and manuscript preparation. The second and third authors, as corresponding authors, conducted the survey, analyzed the data, and wrote up the results of this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data used for this study is available upon request from the researchers.

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